

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Morphology and phase analysis of cordierite ceramic foams with Ag nanoparticles

To cite this article: J. Kupková *et al* 2025 *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* **1337** 012004

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Millimeter-Wave Dielectric Properties of Cordierite/Indialite Glass Ceramics](#)
Hitoshi Ohsato, Jeong-Seog Kim, A-Young Kim *et al.*
- [Development of Cordierite Honeycomb Ceramics Using Cordierite Waste](#)
C Mongkolkachit, P Aungkavattana, W Gosuphan *et al.*
- [Effect of sintering process and additives on the properties of cordierite based ceramics](#)
M Rundans, I Sperberga, G Sedmale *et al.*

The Electrochemical Society
Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

249th
ECS Meeting
May 24-28, 2026
Seattle, WA, US
Washington State
Convention Center

Spotlight Your Science

**Submission deadline:
December 5, 2025**

SUBMIT YOUR ABSTRACT

Morphology and phase analysis of cordierite ceramic foams with Ag nanoparticles

J. Kupková¹, G. Kratošová¹, K. Čech Barabasová¹, G. Simha Martynková¹

¹Nanotechnology Centre, CEET, VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, 17.listopadu 2172/15, 708 00 Ostrava, Czech Republic

*E-mail: jana.kupkova@vsb.cz

Abstract. Direct foaming using H₂O₂ solution was successfully applied to the preparation of cordierite ceramic foams. Cordierite ceramics were synthesized especially from the natural materials: kaolinite, talc and vermiculite, supplemented with Al₂O₃. Ag nanoparticles were prepared by green method from plant extract and after all decorated on ceramic materials. The presence of Ag nanoparticles in cordierite ceramic materials was confirmed by XRD and SEM analysis.

1. Introduction

Cordierite (2MgO·2Al₂O₃·5SiO₂) belongs to the magnesium aluminosilicate minerals and shows many specific properties such as good thermal stability, low thermal expansion coefficient, strong thermal shock resistance and high temperature resistance [1, 2, 3].

The properties of final cordierite ceramics depend on the nature of used precursors, their molar ratio, on the presence of impurities or additives and on the processing conditions. As sources of aluminium, silicon and magnesium can be used a lot of different starting materials including a mixtures of individual oxides MgO, Al₂O₃ and SiO₂, or mixtures of natural raw materials such as kaolinite, talc, vermiculite, gibbsite, magnesite, feldspar, fly ash, asbestos tailing, various clays or other minerals [1, 4, 5, 6, 7]. Traditionally, the solid-state sintering of many kinds of materials, corresponding to the chemical composition of cordierite, is used for obtaining of cordierite ceramics [3]. Another way how to prepare the cordierite ceramic with closed porosity is using of pore formers or using of foaming method.

Direct foaming represents cost effective and relatively easy way to obtain highly porous ceramic materials. The total porosity of foamed ceramics is influenced by amount of gas incorporated into the suspension or liquid medium during the foaming [8]. Li et al. (2015) used the combination of direct foaming and slip casting for fabrication of cordierite foams and also studied the influence of dispersant (Arabic gum) on the porosity, bulk density and thermal conductivity. Their results showed the maximum open porosity 87.65 % at 0.8 wt.% Arabic gum content and these prepared foam ceramics can have potential for use as the thermal insulators [9]. Hui et al. (2021) successfully synthesized cordierite-based ceramic foams by the combination of coal fly ash, asbestos tailing, yellow sand and commercial alumina as starting materials in pre-ceramic mixtures [1].

Silver nanoparticles can be synthesized by green method from aqueous plant extract and AgNO₃ as Ag precursor. Generally, the plant extracts contain variety of phytochemicals such as alkaloids, phenolics, flavonoids and terpenoids, vitamins and enzymes which cause the reduction of metal ions into metal nanoparticles and alongside stabilization [10, 11].

The aim of this study was to produce cordierite ceramic foams enriched with Ag nanoparticles for their possible energy or environmental applications.

2. Materials, procedure and methods

2.1 Materials

For synthesis of cordierite ceramics, the natural clay minerals were used: kaolinite from locality Horní Bříza, Czech Republic (supplied by LB Minerals Ltd., Czech Republic), talc KT5 from Egypt (Koltex Color, Ltd., Czech Republic) and vermiculite from Bulgaria deposit (Grena, Ltd., Czech Republic) and commercial aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3 , Lach-Ner, Ltd. Czech Republic). Raw vermiculite was, firstly, grinded in planetary ball mill (Fritsch Pulverisette) for 20 min by 500 rpm and then sieved in order to prepare the particle size fraction less than 0.040 mm. Kaolinite and talc were only sieved for obtaining the same particle size fraction. Aqueous solution (3 %) of hydrogen peroxide (30 % H_2O_2 , from Mach Chemikalie, Ltd., Czech Republic) was used as foaming agent for the preparation of porous ceramics. The plant *Urtica dioica* was tested as a source of active phytochemical constituents for bioreduction and stabilization of silver nanoparticles in a green synthesis approach. As a silver ions precursor 50 mmol.dm⁻³ silver nitrate was used (AgNO_3 ; Mach Chemikalie, Ostrava, Czech Republic).

2.2. Experiment work

2.2.1 Biosynthesis of Ag nanoparticles

At first, the leaves of plant biomass *Urtica dioica* were dried at 50°C in the laboratory drying oven (Memmert) several hours. 5 g of dried plant leaves (Fig. 1a) was immersed in 1000 ml hot distilled water (80 °C). After 10 minutes, the extract was first quickly decanted, then filtered and cooled down to the room temperature (Fig. 1b). Fresh plant extract was immediately used for bioreduction of nanosilver from AgNO_3 precursor. The prepared plant extract was mixed with AgNO_3 solution in the 1:1 ratio (Fig. 1c) and kept in a dark at 5 °C till next day thus obtaining Ag nanoparticles.

Figure 1. The leaves of *Urtica dioica* (a), plant extract (b) and solution with Ag nanoparticles (c).

2.2.2. Synthesis of cordierite foams

The composition of the pre-ceramic mixtures (Table 1) was based on the previous works [12-14]. At first, the ceramic slurries were prepared: 10 g of mechanically homogenized pre-ceramic mixtures for cordierite ceramics was mixed with small amount of water and stirred 5 min. Then, 10 ml of 3 % H_2O_2 was added and stirred for 5 min. Then, the suspensions were poured into the ceramic calcination molds and inserted into the laboratory drying oven (Memmert) heated at

60°C over night. After this step, the samples were placed into the high temperature tube furnace (STT-1700-12, Sentro Tech Corp) and sintered in air at 1300 °C for 1 hour in order to obtain strong ceramic foams.

Table 1. The labelling and composition of the pre-ceramic mixtures for cordierite foams.

	Talc	Kaolinite	Vermiculite	Al ₂ O ₃
TKV	40	47	13	-
TKAl	40	47	-	13
TKVAl	30	20	30	20

2.2.3. Decoration of cordierite foams with Ag nanoparticles

The sintered ceramic foams were cut into the squares and impregnated by dipping into an aqueous suspensions of Ag nanoparticles for 24 h. Then, the cordierite squares were pull out from colloid suspensions and dried at 60°C over night. Finally, the cordierite foams with Ag nanoparticles were thermal treated in muffle furnace at 200°C for 2 hours in order to fix the silver nanoparticles in the ceramic samples.

2.3. Characterization methods

The X-ray powder diffraction (XRD) analysis was performed using the diffractometer Ultima IV (RIGAKU, Japan) equipped with scintillation detector, CuK α radiation and NiK β filter. Powder samples were measured using Bragg-Brentano arrangement in ambient atmosphere, standard sample holder, and conditions 40 kV, 40 mA, scanning rate 3 °/min. Phase analysis was evaluated by database PDF-2 Release 2022.

Zeta-potential was measured by a nanoparticle analyzer HORIBA Nanopartica SZ-100 (Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a microprocessor unit to directly calculate the Zeta-potential. The Zeta-potential values were calculated from the Smoluchowski equation.

The nanocomposite morphology was investigated using scanning electron microscope (SEM) JEOL JSM-7610F Plus (Tokyo, Japan). The samples were coated with a gold to avoid sample charging. SEM images were obtained using both back-scattered and secondary electrons (COMPO mode, SEI mode). To analyse the morphology and size of silver nanoparticles synthesized via biotechnological method, transmission mode at 30 keV (STEM) and dark-field imaging was employed. A drop of the nanoparticle-containing solution was placed onto a Cu-form var grid, and after drying, the grid was mounted in a sample holder for observation.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterization of Ag nanoparticles

Figure 2a shows the SEM image of Ag nanoparticles in colloid solution after biosynthesis. The XRD pattern of prepared Ag nanoparticles (Fig. 2b) shows the reflections in the position 2θ 38.11°

and 64.51° corresponding to silver phase (PDF card no. 01-071-3762). The other reflections were assigned to the AgCl phase (PDF card no. 01-071-5209).

Figure 2. SEM image of silver nanoparticles solution – STEM DF observation - Ag nanoparticles with stabilization coating (light gray) (a) and XRD pattern of Ag nanoparticles (b).

Zeta-potential of the Ag nanoparticles solution are appropriate for characterisation of the nanoparticles stability and identify their surface charge. The measurement was performed in two steps. First, the original Ag nanoparticle solution was measured statically in a cuvette, the Zeta-potential value was -36.5 mV at a temperature of 24°C . In the second step, 10 ml of the Ag nanoparticle solution was mixed with 150 ml of distilled water, after which a dynamic measurement was performed at a temperature of 23.7°C in the range of 3 - 13 pH. The measurement results are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Zeta-potential of Ag nanoparticles solution.

Zeta-potential values ranged over the entire pH range from -32.6 to -38.9 mV. Slight deviations of the values were measured in the range of 8 and 9 pH, when the Zeta-potential values reached the highest values, and conversely, at pH 11 there was a significant decrease to -22.3 mV. This decrease can be attributed to the formation of a strong electrical response during the measurement, which caused a weak mutual interaction between the nanoparticles. The results of both measurements indicate that the prepared suspension of Ag nanoparticles is stable, which

suggest greater electrostatic repulsion between the particles and ultimately stability. A minimum Zeta-potential value of ± 30 mV is required for stable nanosuspension [15]. The negative Zeta-potential value observed in silver nanoparticles may be due to the potential capping of the bioorganic components present in the plant's extracts [16].

3.2. Characterization of Ag-cordierite ceramics

3.2.1. X-ray diffraction analysis

The XRD patterns of Ag decorated cordierite foam samples were very similar (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. XRD patterns of cordierite foams decorated with Ag nanoparticles.

The crystalline indialite $\text{Mg}_2\text{Si}_5\text{Al}_4\text{O}_{18}$ (In; PDF card No. 01-089-1485) was identified as the main phase for all synthesized ceramics. The ceramic TKVAl_Ag additionally showed the reflections corresponding to spinel MgAl_2O_4 (S; PDF card No. 01-075-4035) as secondary phase and protoenstatite (E; PDF card No.01-074-0816) as minor phase. The ceramic sample TKV_Ag showed in addition to In, the reflection of protoenstatite and spinel phases. The ceramic TKAl_Ag prepared from pre-ceramic mixture containing talc, kaolinite and alumina contained only the reflections corresponding to indialite without another admixtures. The reflections belonging to silver phase (*; PDF card No. 01-087-0720) with cubic crystal system were observed for all ceramics. The reflections corresponding to silver were the most intensive at ceramic sample TKVAl_Ag.

3.2.2. Scanning electron microscopy

The image in Z-contrast mode shows (Fig. 5) that the ceramic TKAl_Ag is not decorated with silver nanoparticles evenly (silver nanoparticles = brighter parts on image). This is probably due to the static exposure of both components, i.e. silver nanoparticle solution and ceramic cubes. However, there are probably also activated sites where silver nanoparticles preferentially adhere.

Figure 5. SEM images of cordierite ceramics decorated with Ag nanoparticles TKAl_Ag. The sample was crushed in a mortar.

Triangular, hexagonal or truncated triangular nanoplates with the edge under 50 nm were observed (Fig. 6) as well as polygonal nanoparticles on all prepared ceramic samples (here documented in detail for sample TKV_Ag).

Figure 6. SEM images of cordierite ceramics TKV_Ag - size and morphology of green synthesized silver nanoparticles. The sample was crushed in a mortar.

The characteristics of this sample TKVAL_Ag (Fig. 7) are comparable to those of the previous two. Silver nanoparticles were also found to be localized at the edges of the ceramic particles, as can be seen in this image.

Figure 7. SEM images of cordierite ceramics decorated with Ag nanoparticles TKVAL_Ag. The sample was crushed in a mortar.

On the Fig. 8, we see the morphology of ceramic TKVAL_Ag in a piece sample (uncrushed). The SEM image in a COMPO regime using back-scattered electrons clearly shows the places, where nanosilver is concentrated (brighter parts) as well as a porous character of ceramic foam material.

Figure 8. SEM images of piece cordierite ceramics TKVAL_Ag uncrushed.

4. Conclusion

Synthesized cordierite ceramics were primarily composed from crystalline phase indialite (high temperature form of cordierite). As secondary phases were identified spinel and protoenstatite. The addition of H_2O_2 into pre-ceramic slurries caused the formation of pores in cordierite ceramic materials. The final cordierite foams decorated with Ag nanoparticles can exhibited catalytic or antibacterial properties. These materials may have potential in energy storage e.g. as separators or solid electrolytes and in environmental applications. The utilization of low cost, natural raw materials sustainability and safety of the materials is reached.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository ZENODO at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15752302> [17].

Acknowledgements

The work was supported by the project MATUR - Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komensky Operational Program (project reg. No.

CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631), the REFRESH – Research Excellence For REgion Sustainability and High-tech Industries (project reg. No. CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048) via the Operational Program “Just Transition” and TAČR Development of an “environmentally friendly” system for anti-corrosion surface treatment of transport infrastructure equipment (SS07020007).

References

- [1] Hui T, Sum HJ, Peng TJ 2021 *Journal of Alloys and Compounds* **885** 160967.
- [2] Goren R, Ozgur C, Gocmez H 2006 *Ceramics International* **32** 53-56.
- [3] Chowdhury A, Maitra S, Das S, Sen A, Samanta GK, Datta P 2007 *Interceram - International Ceramic Review* **56** 18-22.
- [4] Valášková M 2015 *Ceramics-Silikáty* **59** 331-340.
- [5] Kalendová A, Kupková J, Urbášková M, Měřinská D 2024 *Minerals* **14** 93.
- [6] Goren R, Ozgur C, Gocmez H 2006 *Ceramics International* **32** 53-56.
- [7] Obradović N, Rusmirović J, Filipović S, Kosanović D, Marinković A, Radić D, Pavlović V 2020 *Desalination and Water Treatment* **192** 283-296.
- [8] Ahmad R, Ha J-H, Song In-H 2014 *Journal of Korean Powder Metallurgy Institute* **21** 389 – 398.
- [9] Li Y, Cao W, Feng J, Gong L, Cheng X 2015 *Advances in Applied Ceramics* **114** 465-470.
- [10] Kratošová G, Holišová V, Konvičková Z, Ingle AP, Gaikwad S, Škrlová K, Prokop A, Rai M, Plachá D 2019 *Biotechnology Advances* **37** 154-176.
- [11] Singh M, Shabir S, Deopa AS, Raina SR, Bantun F, Jalal NA, Abdel-Razik NE, Jamous YF, Alhumaidi MS, Altammar KA, Hjazi A, Singh SK, Vamanu E 2022 *Antibiotics* **11** 1690.
- [12] Valášková M, Simha Martynková G, Smetana B, Študentová S 2009 *Applied Clay Science* **46** 196-201.
- [13] Valášková M, Zdrálková J, Simha Martynková G, Smetana B, Vlček J, Študentová S 2014 *Ceramics International* **4** 8489-8498.
- [14] Valášková M, Simha Martynková G 2010 *Journal of Scientific Conference Proceedings* **2** 49-52.
- [15] Aruna A, Nandhini R, Karthikeyan V, Bose P 2014 *Asian Journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences* **4**, 1–6.
- [16] Edison T JI, Sethuraman MG 2012 *Process Biochemistry* **47**, 1351–1357.
- [17] Kupková J, Kratošová G, Čech Barabaszová K, Simha Martynková G 2025[Data set] Zenodo, 2025.